

A Study of the Interaction between Thionyl Chloride and Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene Group. Part II. Conversion of Sulphoxides into Sulphides.

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While studying the action of thionyl chloride on malon-diphenylamide, it was found that if the reaction mixture was heated for more than four hours, a yellowish-white crystalline substance was precipitated. This compound was found to have the constitution, $(C_6H_5NH\cdot CO)_2C:S:C(CO\cdot NHC_6H_5)_2$ (I)

This behaviour of malon-diphenylamide is not surprising in view of the fact that thionyl chloride does react with different substances, giving rise to different products, depending on the conditions of the experiment (Michaelis and Philips, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 559; Sprauge, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 321; Jassinari, *Gazzetta*, 1890, 20, 362; Voswinkel, *Pharm. Z.*, 1895, 40, 241; Loth and Michaelis, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2540; Michaelis and Godchaux, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 553; Michaelis and Schindlar, *Annalen*, 1899, 310, 137).

A sulphide similar to the above was also obtained by Michaelis and Philips (*loc. cit.*) by the interaction of thionyl chloride and acetoacetic ester, to which they attributed the constitution (II).

The course of the reaction was explained by them on the assumption that thionyl chloride decomposes into sulphur dichloride and sulphuryl chloride; and the sulphur dichloride thus formed reacts with the ester as under:—

(II)

Michaelis and Loth observed that thionyl chloride reacted as under, with phenols, the final products of the reaction being sulphides:

(A)

(B)

Here the formation of sulphides from sulphoxides was attributed by them to "the reducing action of thionyl chloride." This was supported by the fact that the substance (B), on treatment with nitric acid, gave the substance (A).

It must, however, be pointed out that the formation of the sulphides from sulphoxides, as observed here, cannot be explained on any of the above hypotheses. The hypothesis of Michaelis and Philips presupposes the assumption that thionyl chloride decomposes into sulphur dichloride and sulphuryl chloride. The reaction of sulphur dichloride with substances containing the reactive methylene group has already been studied in this laboratory by Naik and Jadhav (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 261), and in no case was a sulphide of the type represented by Michaelis and Philips obtained, the compounds formed having the constitution—

Again Naik and Shah (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 11) have observed during the investigation of the action of sulphuryl chloride on the same substances, that chloro-compounds of the type,

are formed. Finally the chlorine disengaged as per (4) above would produce chloro-compounds similar to the above (*cf.* West, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 100). Had the course of the reaction been as represented by Michaelis and Philips or Michaelis and Loth, compounds of the type (C), (D), (E), or (F) should have been obtained, whereas during the present work no such compounds were isolated.

Further, if the reaction proceeded as represented by Michaelis and Loth, the resulting sulphide would possess the constitution (G), thus :

whereas the sulphides obtained here have the constitution,

That the sulphides have the constitution assigned to them as above follows from the fact that, thio-bis-malon-diphenylamide when hydrolysed with caustic alkali yields aniline as one of the products of hydrolysis. From this it is clear that the sulphur is neither attached to the nitrogen nor to any of the carbon atoms in the nucleus.

From the above considerations, one is led to suggest that the course of the reaction in the present case is entirely different from that represented by Michaelis and Phillips or Michaelis and Loth. The formation of the sulphides from the sulphoxides can be well explained in the following manner:—

where R may be a tolyl, a phenyl or a naphthyl grouping.

This reaction may proceed either (i) spontaneously, or (ii) in the presence of a catalyst (here thionyl chloride acts as the catalyst). In order to decide this point freshly prepared malon-diphenylamide sulphoxide was heated in dry benzene solution (a) alone, (b) in the presence of thionyl chloride, (c) in the presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas, and (d) in the presence of iodine. In experiment (a) the original malon-diphenylamide was obtained back; whereas in all the other cases a distinct steady evolution of sulphur dioxide was perceived and the sulphide was isolated as the final product. This definitely points to the conclusion that the sulphides are formed from the sulphoxides under the influence of the catalysts such as, thionyl chloride, hydrochloric acid gas or iodine.

The investigation in connection with the formation of sulphides

from sulphoxides was carried out in the case of the sulphoxides obtained from the following amides:—

(1) Malon-diphenylamide, (2) malon-di-*o*-tolylamide, (3) malon-di-*m*-tolylamide, (4) malon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (5) malon di- α -naphthylamide, (6) malon-di- β -naphthylamide, (7) malon-monophenylamide, and (8) malon-mono-*m*-tolylamide.

In all the cases sulphides similar to (H) were obtained, except in (5) and (6), where besides these sulphides, by-products not containing sulphur and having melting points higher than those of the original amides were obtained. These are still under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thio-bis-malon-diphenylamide (I).—Malon-diphenylamide (1.2 g.) was heated with thionyl chloride (0.9 g.) for four hours, after which a solid began to separate. The reaction was continued till there was no further separation of the solid. The compound was filtered after cooling, and washed with dry petroleum (b. p. 50°-60°). It was then boiled with dry petroleum to remove the adhering colour and crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 196°. It is fairly soluble in benzene, alcohol and acetic acid, but insoluble in petroleum and water. (Found: S, 6.07; N, 10.62. $C_{30}H_{24}N_4O_4S$ requires S, 5.96; N, 10.44 per cent.)

Action of dry Hydrochloric Acid on Malon-diphenylamide Sulphoxide.—One g. of freshly prepared sulphoxide was dissolved in 25 c.c. of dry benzene and heated under reflux. Dry hydrochloric acid gas was then slowly passed through this solution. After some time a solid began to separate. The reaction was carried on till there was no evolution of sulphur dioxide. It was filtered and washed with petroleum; it was found to be identical with (I) obtained above.

Action of Iodine.—The above sulphoxide (1 g.) was dissolved in 25 c.c. of dry benzene and 0.4 g. of iodine was added to it. The mixture was heated under reflux for about half an hour, when a solid began to separate. When the evolution of sulphur dioxide had ceased, the compound was filtered and washed with alcohol. It was crystallised from alcohol and subsequently found to be identical with the thio-bis-malon-diphenylamide, obtained in the last two cases.

Hydrolysis of Thio-bis-malon-diphenylamide.—The thio-compound (3 g.) was refluxed with caustic potash (7 g.) dissolved in 10 c.c.

of water, for two hours. A heavy liquid separated out; the mixture was extracted with ether, which on evaporation left a liquid, which was identified as aniline. The aqueous solution was evaporated on a water-bath when a solid was obtained, which on treatment with hydrochloric acid evolved hydrogen sulphide. In all probability the "thio"-grouping was decomposed during the hydrolysis giving rise to potassium sulphide, which evolved hydrogen sulphide.

Thio-bis-malon-di-o-tolylamide.—It was similarly prepared from 1.5 g. of the amide and 0.9 g. of thionyl chloride by heating for four hours. The compound was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m. p. 214°. It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum and water. (Found: S, 5.07. $C_{34}H_{32}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 5.41 per cent.)

Thio-bis-malon-di-m-tolylamide.—It was prepared like the previous compound. The substance was precipitated by slowly adding the solution to a large amount of petroleum. This was repeatedly done by dissolving the compound in benzene and reprecipitating with petroleum till the melting point was constant. It is a dirty yellow substance, m. p. 164°. It is soluble in benzene and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum. (Found: S, 5.45. $C_{34}H_{32}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 5.41 per cent.)

Thio-bis-malon-di-p-tolylamide.—It was prepared as usual. The precipitated substance was filtered and washed with petroleum, and then boiled with alcohol to remove the adhering colour. It is a deep yellow substance and melts at 198°. It is very soluble in acetic acid and sparingly soluble in benzene and alcohol, but insoluble in petroleum. (Found: S, 5.71. $C_{34}H_{32}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 5.41 per cent.)

Thio-bis-malon-di- α -naphthylamide.—Malon-di- α -naphthylamide (1.7 g.) was refluxed in benzene with 0.9 g. of thionyl chloride, for four hours. A substance was precipitated, which was filtered. On examination it was found to contain no sulphur (m.p. 248°). The filtrate was then added to a large amount of petroleum, when a compound was precipitated. After repeated reprecipitations, it was found to melt at 132°. It is very soluble in benzene and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum. (Found: S, 4.04. $C_{46}H_{32}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 4.34 per cent.)

Thio-bis-malon-di- β -naphthylamide.—This was prepared like the previous compound. The substance precipitated during heating contained no sulphur and melted at 265°. The "thio" compound was precipitated from the solution by petroleum. After purification it

melts at 146° . It is a dirty yellow substance soluble in benzene and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum. (Found: S, 4.66. $C_{16}H_{21}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 4.34 per cent.).

Thio-bis-malon-monophenylamide.—It was prepared like the other thio-compounds. After repeated reprecipitations, it was found to melt at 114° . It is soluble in benzene and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum. (Found: S, 8.46. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 8.33 per cent.).

Thio-bis-malon-mono-m-tolylamide.—This was prepared as usual. It is a yellow substance, m.p. 123° . It is soluble in benzene and acetic acid but insoluble in petroleum and water. (Found: S, 7.58. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4S$ requires S, 7.77 per cent.).

The authors desire to record their gratitude to the Government of His Highness the Gaekwar of Baroda for a grant which has defrayed the expenses incurred in this work. One of the authors (M.M.P.) also desires to express his gratitude to H.H. the Maharaja of Bhavnagar for a scholarship which enabled him to carry on this work.

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Received November 2, 1929.